

IJTIMOYIY BEGONALASHUVNING OLDINI OLISHDA MA'NAVYI-MARIFIY ISLOHOTLARNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Bugungi globallashuv zamonida yoshlar qalbida va ongida mafkuraviy bo'shliq paydo bo'lmoqda natijada hayotimizga yangi-yangi tushunchalar paydo bo'lmoqda "ommaviy madaniyat"ning ko'rinishlaridan biri hisoblangan "ijtimoiy begonalashuv" tushunchasi bugungi kunda bir tom ostida yashayotgan qarindoshlar o'rtasida ham kuzatilayotgani achinarli holat. Anashu maqsadda mamlakatimizda bir qator qonunlar, me'yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlar qabul qilinmoqda yoshlarning bo'sh vaqtini mazmunli o'tkazish, ularda mafkuraviy imunitetni shakllantirishga qaratilgan davlat dasturlarining qabul qilinishi har bir mamlakatimiz fuqarosining baxt-saodatiga xizmat qilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Davlat dasturi, ijtimoiy begonalashuv, islohot, siyosat, immunitet, fuqarolik, korrupsiya, ma'naviyat, madaniyat.

THE ROLE OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS IN PREVENTING SOCIAL ALIENATION

Abstract. In today's era of globalization, an ideological vacuum is emerging in the hearts and minds of young people, as a result of which new concepts are emerging in our lives. It is a sad fact that the concept of "social alienation", which is considered one of the manifestations of "mass culture", is observed even among relatives living under the same roof today. For this purpose, a number of laws, regulatory and legal documents are being adopted in our country. The adoption of state programs aimed at meaningful spending of young people's free time, the formation of ideological immunity in them serves the happiness of every citizen of our country.

Keywords: State program, social alienation, reform, politics, immunity, citizenship, corruption, spirituality, culture.

РОЛЬ ДУХОВНО-ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ РЕФОРМ В ПРЕДОТВРАЩЕНИИ СОЦИАЛЬНОГО ОТЧУЖДЕНИЯ

Аннотация. В сегодняшнюю эпоху глобализации в сердцах и умах молодых людей возникает идеологический вакуум, в результате чего в нашей жизни появляются новые понятия. Понятие «социальное отчуждение», которое считается одним из проявлений "массовой культуры", сегодня является обычным явлением среди родственников, живущих под одной крышей. Это печальная ситуация, которая также наблюдается между. С этой целью в нашей стране принимается ряд законов и нормативно-правовых документов.

Принятие государственных программ, направленных на содержательное проведение свободного времени молодежи и формирование у нее идеологического иммунитета, служит счастьем каждого гражданина нашей страны.

Ключевые слова: Государственная программа, социальное отчуждение, реформа, политика, иммунитет, гражданство, коррупция, духовность, культура.

Bugungi kunda yoshlarni milliy g`urur va iftixor tuyg`usi baland, mustaqil fikrli, istiqol va tarqqiyot g`oyalariga sadoqatli, o`z oilasi – Vataniga cheksiz muhabbat ruhida tarbiyalash begonallashuv muammosining oldini olishdagi eng samarali usul hisoblanadi va bu borada mamlakatimiz mustaqillika erishgan dastlabgi kundan boshlab bugungi kungacha bo`lgan davrda juda ham ko`plab samarali ishlar amalga oshirildi. Mustaqillikning ilk kunlaridayoq ”Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati asoslari to`g`risida”gi Qonun qabul qilinishining o`zi bu sohaning nechog`lik ahamiyatli ekanligini anglatib turibdi. Ushbu qonun 2016-yil 14-sentabrda Yangi tahrirda qabul qilinib yangi mohiyat kasb etdi. 2016-yilda “Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini amalga oshirishga qaratilgan qo`shimcha chora-tadbirlar Davlat dasturi” ning qabul qilinishi ma`naviy-ma`rifiy sohadagi islohotlarning izchilligi va uzluksizligini ta`minlashga xizmat qildi. Ta`lim tizimida 2 bosqichli islohotlar amalga oshirildi. Biroq 25 yillik tajribada natijalar tahlili bu jarayonni yangi bosqichga ko`tarishni taqozo qildi. Shu bois Sh. Mirziyoyev tomonidan 2017-yil 7-fevralda 2017-2021-yillarda “O`zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo`yicha harakatlar strategiyasi to`g`risida”gi Farmon qabul qilindi. Bu xalqning ijtimoiy begonallashuvini oldini olishga yo`nalgan maxsus dastur bo`lib, unda jamiyatning barcha sohalaridagi bo`shliqlarga to`la barham berish va O`zbekistonning dunyo hamjamiyatida munosib o`rin egallashi maqsadi yotadi. Hozirgi kunda begonallashuv muammosini boshlang`ich nuqtada – mahallalarda bartaraf etish boshlandi.

Mahalla faollari kengashining tashkil etilishi, unda aholi barcha qatlamlari bilan muloqot qilinishi muhim ahamiyat kasb etib, xalqning dardini eshitish harakati boshlandi.

Prezidentimiz Sh. Mirziyoyevning 2016-yil 22-noyabrda “2017-2020-yillarda shaharlarda arzon ko`p kvartirali uylarni qurish va rekonstruksiya qilish dasturini amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to`g`risidagi” Qarori ijrosi yuzasidan bapo etilayotgan uy-joylar aholining keng qatlami uchun zamonaviy va shinam uylardan foydalanish darajasini tubdan oshirish, yer resurslaridan oqilona foydalanishni ta`minlashga xizmat qilmoqda. Bunday zamonaviy uylar yurtimiz ko`rkiga ko`rk qo`shish va aholi turmush farovonligini yuksaltirish bilan birga, odamlarda davlatga, ertangi kunga ishonch tuyg`usini yanada mustahkamlab, ijtimoiy begonallashuv muammosi jarayoniga qarshi immunitetni mustahkamlamoqda. Ta`lim sifati faqat shaklda namoyon bo`lib, uning mazmuni talabga javob bermaganligi aniqlanganidan keyin ta`lim sohasida islohotlar bo`yicha 2017-yilning 20-aprelda “Oliy ta`lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish

chora-tadbirlari tog'risi"da birinchi qaror, 2018-yil 5-iyunda esa "Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim sifatini oshirish va ularning mamlakatda amalga oshirilayotgan keng qamrovli islohotlarda faol ishtirokini ta'minlash bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida" ikkinchi qaror qabul qilingan. Bu qarorlarda iqtidorli talabalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash, faol mehnat qilayotgan professor-o'qituvchilarni munosib rag'batlantirish nazarda tutilgan bo'lib, shu orqali ular qalbidagi ijtimoiy begonalashuvni oldini olish va bartaraf etish masalasi qo'yildi.

Bunda eng asosiy g'oya xalqning dardu istaklarini his qilish, ularga yordam berish va asrlar davomidagi xalq va davlat o'rtasidagi - jarlikka barham berish hisoblanadi. Bu ulug'vor maqsad davlat va xalq – keng jamoatchilik birdamligi bilan bajariladi. Zero, O'zbekistonning barcha sohalarida keng qamrovda kadrlar korrupsiyasiga barham berilmas ekan, xalq muammolari hal bo'lmaydi.

Shu boradagi ishlarni muvofiqlashtirish maqsadida 2017-yil 3-yanvarda O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurash to'g'risida"gi Qonuni qabul qilindi. Bugun yurtimizda katta islohotlarni amalga oshirish jarayoni boshlandi. Jamiyatimiz hayotidagi bu islohotlar ijtimoiy begonalashuvni oldini olishga qaratilgan. Bularning eng asosiylari ta'lim, sog'liqni saqlash va xavfsizlikni ta'minlash sohasidagi islohotlardir. Siyosiy sohada hududiy yaqinlikni saqlagan holda teng huquqli iqtisodiy hamkorlikni shakllantirish va yanada rivojlantirish, mustahkamlash masalasi qo'shni davlatlar bilan begonalashuvning oldini olishga harakat bo'lib hisoblanadi. O'zbekiston o'z tanlab olgan mustaqil taraqqiyot yo'lidan — ijtimoiy adolat va qonuniylik tamoyillariga asoslangan, inson huquq va erkinliklarini ta'minlash davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishi sifatida belgilangan demokratik huquqiy davlat va kuchli fuqarolik jamiyati qurish yo'lidan qat'iyat bilan bormoqda.

Mamlakatimiz mustaqillikka erishganidan so'ng O'zbekiston tomonidan ratifikatsiya qilingan birinchi xalqaro-huquqiy hujjat – "Inson huquqlarining umumjahon deklaratsiyasida har bir inson fuqarolik huquqiga ega ekanligi mustahkamlab qo'yilgan". Prezident Shavkat Mirziyoyev 2017-yil 20-dekabr kuni "O'zbekiston Respublikasi fuqaroligiga qabul qilish to'g'risida"gi farmonga imzo chekdi. Ko'p yillardan buyon birinchi marta farmon matni ochiq e'lon qilindi. Unga ko'ra 179 kishi O'zbekiston fuqaroligiga qabul qilindi. Shu munosabat bilan, bugungi kunda fuqarolik berish to'g'risidagi murojaatlarni ko'rib chiqish va bunday yuksak unvonga munosib shaxslarni, eng avvalo "O'zbekiston Respublikasining fuqaroligi to'g'risida"gi Qonun kuchga kirgan vaqtda turli obyektiv va boshqa hayotiy vaziyatlarga ko'ra chet elda bo'lgan respublikaning mahalliy aholisi orasidan O'zbekiston Respublikasi fuqaroligiga qabul qilish to'g'risida asosli qarorlar qabul qilish masalasi muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Mazkur choralarning amalga oshirilishi xalqaro huquqning umum e'tirof etilgan prinsiplariga to'la mos keladi va o'zbek zaminida tug'ilib, o'sib-ulg'aygan hamda Vatanimizning taraqqiyoti va ravnaqiga o'zining munosib hissasini qo'shib kelayotgan shaxslarning manfaatlarini nazarda tutadi va ularda ijtimoiy begonalashuv illati paydo bo'lishining oldini oladi.

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